

TO STUDY THE CURRENT PROBLEMS OF THE HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, a lot of scientific research is being carried out in our country, relying on our historical and spiritual heritage, in the matter of truthful and impartial study of the history of the Uzbek people and their statehood. This article interprets information relevant to the study of the history of Uzbekistan.

In the years of independence, the process of deep internal transformation in the science of history was reflected in the theoretical-methodological, conceptual, substantive and structural changes of the science. Under the influence of new conceptual ideas, many topics began to be observed in a new way. Topics that need Haqqani's interpretation and analysis have been the focus of historians' attention, and this process continues until today in reaching a firm conclusion about some of its conceptual aspects.

Subjects that were forbidden to be studied in the period of the former union, and misinterpreted, were re-examined on the basis of scientificity and objectivity - from the point of view of national independence. The scope of historical research has expanded and new scientific directions have emerged. In particular, the demand and attention to the issues of teaching the history of our country has increased more than ever. Because knowing our rich past history, who we were yesterday, who we are today, the days our people went through before independence and the lessons that can be learned from them, all our people, especially our youth, should know perfectly.

In June 1998, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, in a meeting with a group of historical scientists, set before them the task of studying and researching the history of our nation and our Motherland on new theoretical and methodological bases, researching it on the basis of truthfulness, impartiality and in a new ideological spirit.

As a clear proof of this, in July 1998, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the Institute of History of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan" became an important legal and scientific-theoretical basis for studying the science of history in depth and on the basis of objectivity.

In this sense, an example of this is the fact that many scientific researches are being carried out in our country, textbooks and manuals, monographs, and scientific works are

being written in recent years, based on our historical and spiritual heritage, in the matter of honest and impartial study of the history of the Uzbek people and their statehood.

In his speech at the first organizational meeting of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 12, 2015, the First President of our country, Islam Karimov, once again expressed his opinion on the issues of studying our cultural heritage and past history, in particular, the state of studying and teaching the history of our country, its newest periods in educational institutions. expressed his opinion, "We must never forget what a heavy and helpless legacy we have left from the established regime, how much suffering our people have suffered, the fabrication and slanders of the "cotton case", the evil forces sent from the center, who call themselves "paratroopers", destroy the law, justice, it is necessary to fully disclose the whole truth about the actions that they have made underfoot to the honor and pride of our people. It is necessary to arm our growing youth with the lessons of history, with the truth of history. In our schools, lyceums and colleges, in our higher educational institutions, we should pay more attention to impartial and truthful coverage of these same topics. It should be remembered that a nation and a society that forgets its history will lose its way.

In his lectures, Islam Karimov showed the place and role of the science of history in society, especially in the education of young people, the political, socio-economic situation in the republic on the eve of independence, the authoritarian policy of the Red Empire during the former union, the one-sided policy of the center towards the national republics and what consequences it led to. In May 2015, the Committee on Science, Education, Culture and Sports of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis organized a conference focused on the implementation of this issue, which was set by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov. Prominent historical scientists of our republic, representatives of ministries and agencies responsible for the education system, intellectuals of our country took part in the conference, and expressed their opinions and proposals aimed at ensuring the implementation of the urgent tasks set by Islam Karimov.

In the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the extended session of the Cabinet of Ministers, dedicated to the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2022 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2023, the rich history of our country was presented to the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation among the youth and the population. , the task of developing and implementing a complex of measures in order to widely promote its unique culture and national values, in researching the latest history of Uzbekistan, first of all, objective study of primary sources, impartial and truthful research of historical data, modern scientific theory in evaluating historical processes he set priorities such as the use of methods and the achievement of scientific research that meets international requirements.

It is necessary to fully cover the period of independence both chronologically and in terms of fields of scientific research carried out on the latest history of Uzbekistan. It shows that the main part of the researches on the latest history of Uzbekistan carried out to date are related to the cultural and spiritual life, international relations of Uzbekistan with some

countries. Most of the protected studies cover certain areas, and their scientific analysis is insufficient.

Some of them constitute a factual approach, providing statistical data, describing events. Scientific conclusions aimed at critical study of the problem and finding a solution to the scientific problem, implementation of the results of scientific research, practical suggestions and recommendations are not perfect. The content, quality, state of education of Uzbekistan history textbooks taught in educational institutions today, coverage of our distant and recent history in these textbooks, processes on the verge of gaining independence, today's heroes and how they are covered in textbooks, lesson hours allocated to history, as well as the history of our country. The following suggestions and recommendations can be made regarding a number of important issues, such as the potential, knowledge, and state of scientific research of teachers conducting training in science.

First of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to the content of the state education standards, programs, textbooks, study guides on history and first block subjects taught in the education system of our country, the opinions expressed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev, the principles of the national idea, the ideology of independence.

Secondly, to increase the effectiveness of studying and teaching social and humanitarian sciences and conducting fundamental, practical and innovative projects on them, to transfer their content to current and little-studied areas in the latest history of Uzbekistan, including the history of everyday life, interdisciplinary research, social- it is necessary to focus on the stages of economic development, regional security issues.

Thirdly, it is necessary to create a new generation of textbooks and educational complexes that include electronic and multimedia programs for students in the educational system, especially in higher educational institutions, to achieve full coverage of the need for them, and to increase the volume of lessons on the history of Uzbekistan taught in non-specialist areas of higher educational institutions.

Fourthly, it is necessary to develop the integration of science and education in history, to establish educational laboratories and scientific centers in Uzbekistan, to create in-depth scientific researches that show the importance of the policy implemented in Uzbekistan on peace and stability, inter-ethnic relations, and can demonstrate it as an example to others.

Fifth, it is necessary to develop the mutual creative cooperation between intellectuals, historians, writers, film and theater actors of our country, to create historical works, film and stage works reflecting our rich distant and recent history, and to establish a mechanism for conducting scientific research.

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